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Pilgrims of Hope
A Call to a Renewed Vision of Faith and Mission

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EDITORIAL

Pilgrims of Hope: A Call to a Renewed Vision of Faith and Mission

On May 9, 2024, during the Solemnity of the Ascension of the Lord at St. Peter's Basilica, Pope Francis announced the Jubilee Year 2025. The official inauguration followed on December 24, 2024, marked by the Supreme Pontiff ceremonially 'opening the door' of the Basilica—a powerful gesture symbolizing hope for “a new world where peace and justice reign.”¹ Rooted in Scripture (Lev 25–26),² which speaks of the remission of sins, the forgiveness of debts, and universal pardon, every Jubilee serves as a profound reminder of emancipation, restoration, renewal, and the call to build a just and humane world. It signifies the renewal of broken relationships, the bridging of divides, the instillation of hope, and the collective dream of creating a better future for all.

We are thrilled to celebrate the Jubilee Year 2025 (the 2025th anniversary of the Incarnation of Our Lord), and support the Holy Father in this “event of great spiritual, ecclesial, and social significance in the life of the Church.” Pope Francis states in his February 2022 letter announcing the Jubilee 2025, “We must fan the flame of hope that has been given us, and help everyone to gain new strength and certainty by looking to the future with an open spirit, a trusting heart and far-sighted vision. The forthcoming Jubilee can contribute greatly to restoring a climate of hope and trust as a prelude to the renewal and rebirth that we so urgently desire; that is why I have chosen as the motto of the Jubilee, *Pilgrims of Hope*. This will indeed be the case if we are capable of recovering a sense of universal fraternity and refuse to turn a blind eye to the tragedy of rampant poverty that prevents millions of men, women, young people and children from living in a manner worthy of our human dignity. Here I think in particular of the many refugees forced to abandon their native lands. May the voices of the poor be heard throughout this time of preparation for the Jubilee, which is meant to restore access to the fruits of the earth to everyone.”³ Thus, he gives the theme of hope to reflect on our journey.

¹ Christopher White, “Pope opens 2025 Jubilee dreaming of ‘new world where peace and justice reign’,” *National Catholic Reporter* 24 December 2024 [News Online], accessed <https://www.ncronline.org/vatican/vatican-news/pope-opens-2025-jubilee-dreaming-new-world-where-peace-and-justice-reign>, 15 January 2025.

² Also see Lev 25; Num 36:4; Deut 15:1-12; Luke 4: 18-19; Jn 8: 36; CCC, nos. 2419-2423.

³ Pope Francis, “Letter of the Holy Father to the President of the Pontifical Council for Promoting New Evangelization for the Jubilee 2025,” 11 February 2022, accessed 5 January 2025 from <https://press.vatican.va/content/salastampa/en/bollettino/pubblico/2022/02/11/220211c.html>, .

As a preparation for this jubilee, a synodal process of renewal was started, followed by the study of four documents of the *II Vatican Council*—Constitution on the Sacred Liturgy (*Sacrosanctum Concilium*), Dogmatic Constitution on the Church (*Lumen Gentium*), Dogmatic Constitution on Divine Revelation (*Dei Verbum*), Pastoral Constitution on the Church in the Modern World (*Gaudium et Spes*)—and culminating into the celebration of jubilee with the theme, “Pilgrims of Hope.”

Hope is a transformative state of mind anchored in optimism—the conviction that the future holds the promise of something better and that individuals have the capacity to influence it. It enables people to endure even the deepest suffering, as long as they can perceive a glimmer of light at the end of the tunnel. This spark of hope fuels restoration, making it an essential force for advancing justice, peace, equality, and happiness. Acting as a balm for broken spirits and a remedy for suffering, hope becomes even more profound when paired with faith and the grace of God. As Scripture reminds us (Rom 5:3–5), hope builds resilience, empowering individuals to rise above adversity, rebuild from life’s wreckage, and embrace a life of dignity and purpose.

St. Albert’s College embraced *Hope* as the theme for the academic year 2024–25, weaving it into every facet of campus life. The year commenced with an inspiring inaugural address and continued with daily sermons, meditations, recollections, retreats, and the annual research seminars of both students and staff. The intellectual and spiritual exploration culminated in this special issue of *Sevartham*.

This journal proudly presents a profound compilation of reflections centred on hope—its biblical roots, magisterial teachings, theological depth, and transformative influence on individuals and communities. The diverse contributions featured here illuminate the multifaceted nature of hope, emphasizing its crucial role as a cornerstone of Christian faith and a guiding light for the Church’s mission in an ever-evolving and often challenging world.

The Jubilee Year 2025, titled “Pilgrims of Hope,” serves as a timely inspiration. John B. Barla’s keynote address on the inauguration of the academic year on 9 July 2024 titled, *Pilgrims of Hope: Reflections on Spes Non Confundit*, offers a rich exploration of this theme positioning it within the historical and theological context of jubilee celebrations. Barla’s insights remind us of the Church’s call to foster hope amidst the pressing crises of our time—ecological degradation, social inequality, and spiritual fragmentation. His emphasis on the Eucharist as a unifying force provides a powerful image of hope as a collective journey of restoration and renewal.

From a scriptural perspective, Anupa Kujur's *Biblical Basis of Hope: Exploring Its Foundations, Characteristics, and Impact* sheds light on the enduring and imperishable nature of Christian hope. This article delves into the profound concept of hope as rooted in the Bible, drawing from both the Old and New Testaments. It contrasts biblical hope—characterized by confident expectation and unwavering faith in God's promises—with secular notions of hope, which are often uncertain and fleeting. The discussion highlights the theological dimensions of hope, its integral role in Christian life, and its transformative power to sustain believers amidst trials. It also explores the interrelationship between hope and faith and social, spiritual, and psychological effects of hope.

Similarly, Sam T. Rajkumar's *Pilgrims of Hope: The Psalmist's Pathway to Faith and Restoration* delves into the Psalms, revealing how their language of lament and praise provides a model for believers to cultivate trust and resilience in God's steadfast love. The Psalms express various facets of hope, from lament and trust to praise and confidence and serve as a spiritual guide for believers, particularly in times of adversity. The article contrasts biblical hope, rooted in God's unchanging nature, with worldly hope, which is fragile and reliant on circumstances. The Psalms ultimately provide a model for believers to cultivate enduring hope through trust in God's steadfast love, communal support, and personal spiritual practices.

John Crasta's *Synodality in the Light of Aggiornamento and Kairos of Vatican II* reminds us of the spirit of renewal that Vatican II envisioned. Synodality, as a manifestation of hope, calls for dialogue, inclusivity, and a renewed commitment to the mission of the Church as the people of God. Thus, this article sets the tone for the dogmatic foundation of hope.

Theological reflections also bring hope into dialogue with pressing realities. A. John Kennedy's exploration of Jürgen Moltmann's perspectives in *The God of Hope and the Church of Hope for the Poor* challenges traditional doctrines by presenting a God who suffers in solidarity with humanity. This radical understanding calls for a Church that prioritizes the poor and oppressed, embodying hope in the pursuit of justice and liberation.

Fr. Valerian Lobo in the article, *Basic Ecclesial Communities: the Life of the Church*, explores Basic Ecclesial Communities (BECs) as vital to the Church's synodal journey, aligning with Pope Francis' call for transformation rooted in communion, participation, and mission. Inspired by the Apostolic Age, BECs foster mutual fellowship, deepen faith through shared reflection on God's Word, support the marginalized, and promote justice and care. Recognized universally as a desirable way of being Church,

BECs act as homes of communion and laboratories of faith, embodying listening, discernment, and co-responsibility. Despite challenges, they offer the potential to build vibrant communities of love. The article presents practical suggestions to strengthen BECs in parish life.

This communal and sacramental dimension of hope finds resonance in Leena Fernandes' work, *Eucharist as the Sacrament of Hope*. Fernandes masterfully articulates how the Eucharist bridges the temporal and eternal, nurturing hope in the hearts of believers as they await the fulfillment of God's kingdom. The Eucharist is celebrated not just as a rite, but as a transformative event that binds personal faith with communal and cosmic aspirations.

Hope also finds expression in the dynamism of leadership and formation within the Church. Sanjit Kumar Kujur's *Seminary Formation and Priestly Mission: Hope for a New Jerusalem* outlines a vision for priestly formation that integrates tradition with innovation, preparing leaders who can guide communities toward a just and spiritually vibrant future. Complementing this is Suman Kumar Ekka's *Women Leadership in the Church: A Gift and a Hope*, which highlights the indispensable role of women as equal partners in the Church's mission. Their leadership, rooted in hope, challenges the Church to embrace inclusivity and equity as fundamental to its identity.

Finally, Fr. Santhosh Ekka contextualizes the theme by bringing a transformative aspect of hope amongst the tribal church in his article, *Eco-Spirituality of the Oraon Tribe: A Hope for the World*. Hope, a transformative force, bridges challenges and possibilities, anchoring life in harmony with God, self, others, and nature. The Oraon tribe's Eco-Spirituality embodies this hope through simplicity, community, and respect for creation. Integrating moral and spiritual values into daily life, they demonstrate that hope is a lived reality and not an abstract one. Amid modern ecological and social crises, their ethos of mutual respect, universal brotherhood, and gratitude offers a sustainable model. Rooted in faith and harmony, Oraon spirituality inspires humanity to reconnect with the divine and creation, fostering transformative solutions for the world's pressing challenges.

The present volume also finds a place for a Book Review, *Resounding Faith: Embracing Modern Music in Children's Ministry* authored by Sam T. Rajkumar which offers a refreshing and insightful exploration of the intersection of faith, music, and ministry, presenting a compelling case for the importance of modern musical styles in nurturing young hearts and minds in the Christian faith. The journal concludes with two PhD excerpts from the faculty.

Together, these contributions weave a rich tapestry of hope—one that honours the past, engages the present, and looks to the future with steadfast faith. As pilgrims of hope, the Church and its members are called to embody this virtue in every dimension of life: personal journeys, communal worship, and societal engagement.

Pope Francis captures this beautifully in *Fratelli Tutti*: “Hope speaks to us of a thirst, an aspiration, a longing for a life of fulfillment, a desire to achieve great things, things that fill our heart and lift our spirit to lofty realities like truth, goodness, and beauty” (*FT*, 55). May these reflections inspire us to live as authentic witnesses of hope, shaping a world illuminated by justice, compassion, and the transformative love of God.

Editor

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PILGRIMS OF HOPE: THE PSALMIST'S PATHWAY TO FAITH AND RESTORATION

Sam T Rajkumar¹

Abstract

*The theme of hope in the Psalms encompasses both historical anticipation and present assurance, intertwining the concepts of redemption, liberation, and faith. This paper explores how biblical hope is deeply rooted in God's character, promises, and past actions. In the Old Testament, hope is closely tied to salvation, particularly through the anticipation of a coming Messiah. The New Testament fulfils this hope in Jesus Christ, who embodies redemption and reconciliation. The Psalms serve as a spiritual guide for believers, expressing various facets of hope through different types of psalms—lament, praise, trust, and confidence. They reveal hope as both a personal and communal journey, especially in adversity. This paper highlights the significance of the Hebrew terms *tikvah*, *yachalipu* and *miqveh*, reflecting a confident expectation of God's deliverance, and how the Psalms utilize memory and liturgical recitation to sustain collective hope. The study reveals how the Psalms guide believers in navigating life's challenges by examining key Psalms and the interplay between worldly and biblical hope. Ultimately, the journey offers a model for modern believers to cultivate and sustain hope through trust in God's steadfast love, communal support, and personal spiritual practices.*

1. Introduction

Biblical hope encompasses both historical anticipation and present assurance, weaving together themes of redemption, liberation, and faith. It remains a powerful force that sustains believers across generations. In the Old Testament, hope is closely connected to salvation and redemption. It finds expression through the anticipation of a coming Messiah. The promise of a deliverer who would bring liberation and restoration fuelled the hope of ancient Israelites.² The Israelites' journey from slavery in Egypt to the Promised Land symbolizes hope fulfilled - a journey from bondage to freedom. In the New Testament, hope finds its ultimate fulfilment in Jesus Christ. His life, death, and resurrection provide the foundation for Christian hope. The hope of salvation and redemption centres on Jesus as the Messiah—the one who brings reconciliation between God and humanity. Rabbi Jonathan Sacks³ offers a unique perspective on hope. For him, hope is not merely an expectation or emotion; it's a commentary on the Torah

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² Greg Gaines, "Exploring the Bible Definition of Hope: A Spiritual Insight," *Biblical Definitions*, accessed 2 August 2024, <https://biblicaldefinitions.com/bible-definition-of-hope>.

³ Rabbi Jonathan Sacks (1948-2020) was an influential English Orthodox rabbi, philosopher, theologian, and author. He served as Chief Rabbi of the United Hebrew Congregations of the Commonwealth from 1991 to 2013.

(especially the Exodus narrative) and its relevance to present reality.⁴ Sacks emphasizes trust, love, and a change of identity as key ingredients for addressing radical uncertainty. The biblical God, according to Sacks, represents a particular view of reality - one that inspires hope even amidst challenges.

The theme of “Pilgrims of Hope” in the Psalms carries deep spiritual significance, encapsulating the faith-filled journey of seeking God, facing challenges, and trusting in His promises. The Psalms, with their rich poetic language and deep spiritual insights, offer profound hope to believers navigating various life situations. They serve as a source of survival and resilience providing hope even in dire circumstances. They also offer an uplifting perspective, reminding us that God arms us with strength and secures our way and that God is our unshakable rock and salvation. The Psalms validate our emotions and provide a safe outlet for emotional release and assurance. Furthermore, they bring comfort and peace, encouraging us to keep our eyes on the Lord for security, and urging us to seek God’s face always, rejoicing in His holy name.

2. The Nature of Hope in the Psalms

The Psalms contain various expressions of hope, reflected in key Hebrew terms that convey deep spiritual meaning. One such term is *tikvah* (תִּקְוָה), directly translating to “hope,” as seen in Psalm 69:7, where the psalmist expresses a confident expectation that God will rebuild the cities of Judah.⁵ *Tikvah* represents a trust in God’s promises. Another term, *yachalipu* (יָחַלִּיפוּ), found in Isaiah 40:31, conveys the idea of patiently waiting with hope, expecting God’s intervention and renewal.⁶ Although not exclusively used for hope, *miqveh* (מִקְוֵה) means “a place of hope” or “a source of expectation,” as seen in Jeremiah 14:8, where God is described as Israel’s “hope” and “source of living water” (*miqveh mayim chayim*).⁷ These terms reflect the psalmists’ deep longing, trust, and anticipation of God’s goodness and faithfulness.⁸ In the Psalms, hope is not mere wishful thinking; it is firmly anchored in the character and promises of God.

⁴ Jan Jorrit Hasselaar, *Climate Change, Radical Uncertainty and Hope: Theology and Economics* (Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Press, 2023), 65.

⁵ C. H. Toy, “Rise of Hebrew Psalm-Writing,” *Journal of the Society of Biblical Literature and Exegesis* Vol.7, No.1 (June 1887): 47-60. 49.

⁶ “Hope,” <https://www.sefaria.org>, accessed 8 August 2024, <https://www.sefaria.org/topics/hope?sort=Relevance&tab=sources>.

⁷ James Luther Mays, “The Place of the Torah-Psalms in the Psalter,” *Journal of Biblical Literature* Vol.106, No. 1 (March, 1987): 4.

⁸ Esther Kuhn, “Hope in Hebrew: Tikvah—Hope That Does Not Disappoint,” <https://firmisrael.org>, accessed 21 August 2024 <https://firmisrael.org/learn/hope-in-hebrew-tikvah-hope-does-not-disappoint>.

Worldly hope, often based on circumstances, external factors, and human strength, is a desire or wish for something to happen but lacks a solid guarantee. It is uncertain, relying on changeable circumstances and people, and is subjective, influenced by emotions, trends, and external events. Furthermore, worldly hope is limited by human abilities and knowledge, with examples including weather predictions, personal aspirations, and wishes.⁹ In contrast, biblical hope is rooted in God's promises and character, offering a confident certainty rather than mere wishful thinking. Biblical hope is assured, grounded in God's unchanging nature and past actions, and it is future-centric, looking forward to the fulfilment of God's promises.¹⁰ Unlike worldly hope, it is objective, transcending human limitations and resting on God's reliability. Examples of biblical hope include the hope of salvation through Jesus, healing based on Christ's sacrifice, and the assurance of eternal life.

The Psalms beautifully express hope as trust in God's character. Psalm 1 connects Israel's historical interpretation, as seen in Deuteronomy-Kings, with the personal conduct of individuals, emphasizing that trust in the Lord is demonstrated through a constant concern for God's instruction. By meditating on God's Word, we find both guidance and hope.¹¹ Psalm 19 celebrates God's revelation through creation and His written Word, underscoring the trustworthiness of God's character. Trusting in God's promises requires confidence in His love, mercy, and grace.¹² Similarly, Psalm 119, the longest chapter in the Bible, extols the beauty and value of God's law. Trusting in God's character means delighting in His statutes, seeking His guidance, and relying on His promises, through which we find solace, wisdom, and enduring hope.

The theme of hope in the Psalms highlights a profound contrast between biblical and worldly hope. The Hebrew terms *tikvah*, *yachalipu*, and *miqveh* reflect a deep-rooted faith in God's covenant promises, showcasing hope as a steadfast expectation grounded in God's faithfulness rather than wishful thinking. This hope, sustained through remembrance of God's past actions, becomes a source of resilience in adversity. The Psalms, particularly Psalms 1, 19, and 119, illustrate that hope is not passive but is actively nurtured through meditation on God's Word. Unlike worldly hope, which

⁹ W. W. Meissner, "Notes on the Psychology of Hope," *Journal of Religion and Health* Vol.12, No.1 (January 1973): 7-29. 16.

¹⁰ Nancy Golden, "Biblical hope is not like the world's hope," www.BeADisciple.com, accessed 21 August 2024, <https://beadisciple.com/blog/biblical-hope-is-not-like-the-worlds-hope>.

¹¹ James Luther Mays. "The Place of the Torah-Psalms in the Psalter," *Journal of Biblical Literature* Vol.106, No.1 (March, 1987): 11.

¹² "Faith: Trusting in God's Promises and Character," <https://scripturalthinking.com>, accessed 22 August 2024, <https://scripturalthinking.com/faith-trusting-in-gods-promises>.

is fragile and reliant on shifting circumstances, biblical hope is anchored in the unchanging nature of God, offering believers enduring assurance. In a world fixated on temporal guarantees, the Psalms invite us to cultivate an eternal hope, rooted in trust in God's promises and a life committed to His Word.

3. Expressions of Hope in Different Types of Psalms

The theme of hope within Psalms of Lament is powerfully expressed through the deep anguish, sorrow, and distress found in these prayers, yet they reveal a resilient hope in God's promises. Lament, in both the Old and New Testaments, involves persistent cries to God for salvation during times of suffering or sin, reflecting a confident belief that God hears and responds to our pleas, acting to bring wholeness. Psalms of lament typically follow a pattern: a complaint where the psalmist expresses distress, a petition asking for God's help or deliverance, an affirmation of trust in God's faithfulness and salvation even amid distress, and a resolution where the psalmist ultimately chooses to trust God, rejoicing in His steadfast love, as seen in Psalm 13:5-6. This theme of lament continues in the New Testament, where Jesus, fully human and divine, expressed lament, with His cries from the cross-echoing themes found in Old Testament lament psalms such as Psalms 22, 31, and 69.¹³ Additionally, Romans 7, often viewed as a personal lament, shares verbal and conceptual similarities with Psalm 119, emphasizing the struggle with sin, the cry for salvation, and hope in God's promises.¹⁴

Psalms of Praise, also known as *Tehillim*, serve as the prayerful response of the Chosen People to God's revelation throughout history. While not all psalms are hymns or songs of praise, some specifically celebrate God's marvellous works in nature and history. Central to these praises is the recognition of God as both Redeemer and Creator, with Israel extolling the Lord for their deliverance from Egyptian bondage during the Exodus, His covenant with them, the Law of Moses, and His continual watchful care. Psalms of Praise highlight these loving interactions between God and Israel.¹⁵ Psalm 19, one of the greatest poems in the Psalter, beautifully combines praise for God's creation, as the heavens declare His glory, with reverence for His Law, which serves as the perfect instruction for life. The psalmist's awe and hope stem from contemplating both God's natural wonders and

¹³ June Dickie, review of *Jesus Wept: The Significance of Jesus' Laments in the New Testament* by Rebekah Eklund, *Neotestamentica* Vol.54, No.1 (2020): 162.

¹⁴ Will N. Timmins, "Romans 7 and the Resurrection of Lament in Christ: The Wretched "I" and His Biblical Doppelgänger," *Novum Testamentum* Vol.61, No.4 (2019): 386.

¹⁵ Conleth Kearns, "Psalms of Praise," *The Furrow* Vol.14, No.6 (June 1963): 368-369.

His revealed Word.¹⁶ Similarly, Psalm 130 expresses deep longing and hope as the psalmist waits for the Lord, trusting in His word. Israel is encouraged to hope in the Lord because of His steadfast commitment and abundant redemption, with the psalm emphasizing God's forgiveness and deliverance from iniquities.¹⁷

The theme of hope within Psalms of Trust and Confidence is vividly expressed through unwavering confidence in God's protection, even amid adversity. Psalm 30, attributed to David, reflects his experience during a time of distress, where he prays to God with great confidence for deliverance, recalling God's past mercies. Despite suffering, ridicule from enemies, and a sense of abandonment, David trusts God and commits his fate to Him, eventually celebrating God's goodness as the clouds of trouble clear. He urges all the faithful to love God and take courage.¹⁸ Similarly, Psalm 23, while not explicitly labelled as a psalm of trust, beautifully conveys confidence in God's care through the imagery of God as the Good Shepherd, providing assurance of His presence even in adversity. The psalm speaks of green pastures, still waters, and a table set in the presence of enemies, evoking hope and trust in God's guidance and protection. In Psalm 7, David declares, "O Lord my God, in You I have taken refuge," likening God to a cave that sheltered him from adversaries, embodying the trust and confidence that we too can place in God's unwavering care and protection.¹⁹

Reflecting on hope in the Psalms of Lament, Praise, and Trust reveals a profound interplay between human vulnerability and divine faithfulness. Psalms of Lament demonstrate that hope often emerges through anguish and honest confrontation with pain, exemplified by the structure of complaint, petition, trust, and resolution, as seen in Psalm 13. This hope, rooted in God's promises, is mirrored in the New Testament, where Jesus' cries on the cross resonate with these laments. Psalms of Praise, such as Psalm 19, shift the focus from pain to the celebration of God's creation and salvation, making hope a communal experience rooted in divine mercy. Psalms of Trust, including Psalm 23 and Psalm 30, further illustrate hope as confident assurance in God's ongoing care and protection, transcending mere survival. Overall, the Psalms portray hope as an active, dynamic trust in God, cultivated through lament, deepened in praise, and sustained by

¹⁶ J. Ross Wagner, "From the Heavens to the Heart: The Dynamics of Psalm 19 as Prayer," *The Catholic Biblical Quarterly* Vol.61, No.2 (April, 1999): 247.

¹⁷ Lee Roy Martin, "Lament and Hope in Psalm 130," *Pharos Journal of Theology* Vol.100 (2019): 5.

¹⁸ Ernest Lussier, "The New Latin Psalter: An Exegetical Commentary XIV: Psalm 30 and 31," *The Catholic Biblical Quarterly* Vol.12, No.3 (July 1950): 321-323.

¹⁹ Paul Birston, "Psalms of Trust An Introduction," <https://gospelherald.org>, accessed 23 August 2024, <https://gospelherald.org/psalms-of-trust-an-introduction>.

unwavering confidence in His character, revealing that hope endures not because of circumstances but because of God's steadfast love.

4. The Dynamics of Hope in the Psalms

Psalm 3 illustrates the interplay between fear, doubt, and hope in profound ways. In this Psalm, King David confronts two significant threats: an army led by his own son, Absalom, who seeks to overthrow and destroy him, and attacks questioning his kingship and character. Despite his past mistakes, such as his sin with Bathsheba, David turns to God in prayer. This Psalm teaches us how to bring our fears to God and find strength and peace by resting in our secure gospel identity.²⁰ Overall, the Psalms acknowledge our pain, sorrow, and uncertainty, inviting us to seek comfort and hope in God, who remains steadfast in His love and trustworthy in His promises, even amid our struggles.²¹

The role of memory and remembrance in sustaining hope within the Psalms is a captivating subject. Postexilic psalms, such as Psalms 137-145, utilize remembered space to shape collective memory and hope by recalling Yahweh's historical deeds and the events of the Babylonian exile, which help sustain hope for the future.²² Liturgical recitation also plays a crucial role; psalms that address themes of time, memory, and hope, as well as those that evoke these themes indirectly, contribute to a sense of continuity and anticipation.²³ Through communal recitation, worshippers are connected to their shared history and inspired with hope for the future. Additionally, Mary Rowlandson, a colonial American woman, found solace in the Psalms during her captivity by Native Americans.²⁴ The language of the Psalms helped restore her sense of self amidst immense suffering, providing a linguistic framework for expressing both personal anguish and hope.

The Psalms in the Old Testament offer a profound exploration of eschatological hope, weaving together devotional intimacy with God

²⁰ Lee Lewis, "True Hope in Battling Fear: A Lesson from Psalm 3," <https://www.biblicalcounselingcoalition.org/2022/08/29/true-hope-in-battling-fear-a-lesson-from-psalm-3>, accessed 25 August 2024, <https://www.biblicalcounselingcoalition.org/2022/08/29/true-hope-in-battling-fear-a-lesson-from-psalm-3>.

²¹ Tiffany Christensen, "6 Emotions the Psalms Teach Us and Their Biblical Meanings," <https://biblicalpathway.com>, accessed 27 August 2024, <https://biblicalpathway.com/6-emotions-the-psalms-teach-us-and-their-biblical-meanings>.

²² Marina Kok, "Remembered space: Memory and identity in Psalms 137-145" (M.A. Dissertation, University of Pretoria, 2020).

²³ Emma O'Donnell, "Psalmic Recitation as a Performance of Memory and Hope in Jewish and Christian Prayer," *The Journal of Scriptural Reasoning* Vol.12, No. 1 (November 2013). Accessed 27 August 2024 <https://jsr.shanti.virginia.edu/back-issues/vol-12-no-1-november-2013-music-the-psalms-and-scriptural-reasoning/>.

²⁴ Dawn Henwood, "Mary Rowlandson and the Psalms: The Textuality of Survival," *Early American Literature* 32/2 (1997): 172.

and a deep interest in His actions in history. Theologian Geerhardus Vos emphasizes the dual nature of the Psalms, which serve as a resource for personal prayer and reflection while also containing eschatological themes. The juxtaposition of the Psalms with the Book of Revelation in certain New Testament editions underscores this duality, highlighting their resonance during times of historical upheaval, such as the Reformation or more recent global events.²⁵ The Psalter unites personal devotion with a broader eschatological vision, expressing hope in God's ultimate restoration and renewal. This hope includes the anticipation of a new creation where all things are made new, the end of suffering and societal evil, and the reconciliation and healing of all creation.²⁶ David Mitchell suggests that the Psalms follow a purposeful order, recording eschatological events such as Israel's exile, the appearance of a Messiah, the gathering of Israel, conflicts among nations, suffering, the scattering of Israel in the wilderness, the establishment of Zion, and the prosperity of Israel.²⁷

Psalm 3 vividly illustrates the tension between fear, doubt, and hope, showcasing how David's deep personal crisis transforms into confidence through faith in God's protection. Despite external threats and past failures, David's trust in God's grace turns anguish into hope, emphasizing that hope is a decision to trust amidst uncertainty. This theme of hope is reinforced in postexilic psalms, which use communal memory to preserve hope through the recollection of God's historical acts, a practice echoed in Mary Rowlandson's experience. The Psalms also explore eschatological hope, anticipating ultimate restoration and aligning personal devotion with a broader vision of redemption. David Mitchell's observation of a purposeful order in the Psalms ties historical struggles to a larger theological framework, offering believers comfort and orientation toward a future renewal. Overall, the Psalms present hope as grounded in God's unchanging character and faithfulness, providing strength for navigating life's complexities through a blend of past remembrance and future anticipation.

5. Pilgrims of Hope: The Psalmist's Journey as a Model for Believers

The Psalms offer a profound exploration of the human experience, capturing the journey from despair to hope. While the concept of innocent voluntary suffering to expiate the sins of others isn't explicitly taught in the Psalms, hints of this idea emerge, particularly in the struggles of the just man

²⁵ Geerhardus Vos, "Eschatology of the Psalter," *The Princeton Theological Review* Vol.18 (January, 1920): 1.

²⁶ Charlotte Oyen-Witvliet, et al., "The Eschatological Hope Scale: Construct Development and Measurement of Theistic Eschatological Hope," *Journal of Psychology and Christianity* Vol.41, No.1 (Spring 2022): 16.

²⁷ David C. Mitchell, *Message of the Psalter: An Eschatological Programme in the Book of Psalms* (Sheffield: Sheffield Academic Press, 1997), 15.

whose unrelieved sufferings led some to assume he was being punished for his sins. Psalm 73 reflects this tension, as the psalmist grapples with envy of the wicked's prosperity and the seeming absence of justice for the righteous, stating, "For all the day long I have been stricken, and chastened every morning." Despite these challenges, the Psalms often reveal a deep sense of hope.²⁸ For instance, Psalm 3, though it begins as a conventional prayer, contains the powerful affirmation: "I lay down and slept; I awoke, for the Lord supports me," highlighting the psalmist's trust in God's support even when surrounded by enemies.²⁹ The healing power of the Psalms is evident in their foundational role in Jewish liturgy, providing comfort and expression in various life situations. Psalm 40, for example, captures both despair and hope, emphasizing trust in God's deliverance.³⁰

Psalm 126 is a lyrical gem that captures the shifting moods of life, transitioning from tears to laughter, and sorrow to joy. As part of the Songs of Ascents (Ps 120-134), sung by pilgrims journeying to Jerusalem for festivals, this psalm consists of six verses that convey powerful emotions. In the first section, "The Joyful Dream" (Ps 126: 1-3), the psalmist reflects on the joy of Israel's restoration after exile, describing it as a dream come true. The people's mouths were filled with laughter, and their tongues with singing, as they rejoiced in God's faithfulness and redemption. The second section, "Sowing in Tears, Reaping in Joy" (Ps 126: 4-6), shifts to agricultural imagery, where those who sow in tears are promised a harvest of joy. This mirrors Israel's journey from the sorrow of exile to the joy of return, reflecting the psalmist's trust in God's transformative power. Throughout the psalm, unconquerable faith shines through, as the psalmist recalls how Yahweh had turned their fortunes in the past and expresses confidence that the same God can transform present sorrows into future joy.³¹ The psalm's imagery echoes the conditions of Haggai's time, where laughter and tears coexisted.

Emulating the Psalmist's trust in God during times of trial involves embracing the deep emotions and struggles often expressed in the Psalms. When facing challenges, we can learn from the Psalmists by praying honestly, pouring out our hearts to God, and seeking refuge in Him, trusting that He is our strength even in difficult circumstances. Reflecting on past experiences where God has been faithful helps us to remember His steadfastness. To

²⁸ Michael Baily, "The Messiah in the Psalms," *The Furrow* Vol.15, No.4 (April 1964): 231-232.

²⁹ Ruth Fidler, "A Touch of Support: Ps 3,6 and the Psalmist's Experience," *Biblica* Vol.86, No.2 (2005): 193-198.

³⁰ Jeffrey Newman, "The Healing Power of Psalms: Psalm 40," *European Judaism* Vol.22, No.2 (Winter 89-Spring 90): 20-21.

³¹ John E. McFadyen, "The Messages of the Psalms: Psalm 126," *The Biblical World* Vol.26, No.4 (October 1905): 258-261.

foster and sustain hope, it is important to regularly communicate with God through prayer, seeking His guidance, expressing gratitude, and sharing our hearts. Engaging in worship through singing, reading Scripture, and participating in communal worship services strengthens our connection with God. Additionally, connecting with other believers in a church community provides fellowship, accountability, and encouragement, all of which are essential for spiritual growth.

Living as “Pilgrims of Hope” in a modern context requires a deliberate integration of personal practices and communal support. To sustain hope, it is essential to articulate emotions during times of setbacks or losses, whether through conversations with trusted individuals or by documenting them privately, facilitating the release of negative emotions and redirecting focus toward future possibilities. Cultivating optimism by leveraging personal strengths, challenging counterproductive thoughts, and exploring opportunities rather than constraints is crucial. Additionally, practicing mindfulness allows one to remain present and appreciate the unfolding beauty of life.

The significance of community and fellowship cannot be overstated, as they serve as foundational sources of shared hope. Engaging in a spiritual community involves collectively navigating the journey of faith, celebrating successes, empathizing with struggles, and providing mutual support. Fellowship, which extends beyond superficial interactions, fosters deep connections and friendships within the Christian community, playing a critical role in spiritual development. While discipleship, which involves actively embracing and disseminating the teachings of Jesus, is essential, it is through the strength of community and fellowship that enduring hope is nurtured and sustained.

Thus, the Psalms provide a deep reflection on the human experience, capturing a spectrum of emotions from despair to hope, and highlighting the journey from suffering to joy. Psalm 73 portrays the struggle with perceived injustice and the ultimate resolution found in trusting God’s justice, while Psalm 126 illustrates the transition from lament to joy through the metaphor of sowing and reaping. This theme underscores that joy often emerges from hardship through God’s transformative power. The Psalms emphasize the importance of remembering God’s past faithfulness as a source of strength and hope. In contemporary life, being “Pilgrims of Hope” involves embracing deep emotions through prayer, worship, and communal support, which sustain and renew hope. The Psalms teach that hope is not about the absence of suffering but about trusting God’s presence and faithfulness amidst life’s trials, fostering resilience through both personal spirituality and communal fellowship.

6. Conclusion

The exploration of hope in the Psalms reveals a nuanced and profound understanding of this vital theme, reflecting the intricate relationship between human experiences and divine promises. The Psalms provide a rich tapestry of hope, capturing the multifaceted nature of this enduring virtue as it intersects with suffering, praise, trust, and communal identity.

Biblical hope, as articulated through the Psalms, is not a static or passive expectation but an active and dynamic trust in God's character and promises. It transcends mere wishfulness, rooting itself in the steadfastness of God's nature and His historical faithfulness. This hope is both historical and eschatological, drawing strength from the recollection of past deliverances while anticipating future fulfilment. It offers believers a framework for understanding and navigating life's uncertainties, reaffirming that hope is deeply intertwined with the narrative of divine intervention and redemption.

The Psalms illustrate that hope is inherently relational and communal. The psalmists, through their personal and collective experiences, emphasize the importance of remembering God's past deeds as a source of encouragement and resilience. The communal aspect of hope is particularly evident in the Psalms of Lament, Praise, and Trust, where individual and collective experiences of God's faithfulness are woven into the broader tapestry of Israel's history. This collective dimension underscores the role of shared worship, liturgical recitation, and communal memory in sustaining hope across generations.

Furthermore, the Psalms offer a model for believers navigating their own pilgrimages of hope. They invite individuals to embrace the full spectrum of human emotions, from despair to joy, while maintaining a profound trust in God's unwavering presence and commitment. This pilgrimage involves an honest engagement with one's struggles, an active remembrance of God's past faithfulness, and a continuous pursuit of spiritual and communal support. By integrating personal devotion with communal fellowship, believers can sustain hope even amid life's trials, finding strength in the transformative power of God's promises.

The Psalms ultimately present hope as a profound and resilient force that endures beyond temporary circumstances. It is a testimony to the enduring nature of God's faithfulness, a call to actively engage with one's spiritual journey, and an invitation to find solace and renewal in the broader context of communal worship and remembrance. In embodying the lessons of the Psalms, believers are equipped to face life's uncertainties with a confident and enduring hope, rooted in the assurance of God's everlasting love and redemptive promise.

BOOK REVIEW

Resounding Faith: Embracing Modern Music in Children's Ministry (Bangalore: Omega Book World, 2023), by Sam T. Rajkumar, pp. 129, price ₹ 300.00, ISBN: 978-93-89069-81-5 (Paperback), eISBN: 978-93-89069-82-2 (Kindle).

In the book, *Resounding Faith: Embracing Modern Music in Children's Ministry*, Sam T. Rajkumar offers a refreshing and insightful exploration of the intersection of faith, music, and ministry, presenting a compelling case for the importance of modern musical styles in nurturing young hearts and minds in the Christian faith.

The book is divided into seven chapters, each addressing different aspects of the use of music in ministry, apart from Foreword, Acknowledgments, Preface, Commendation, and Introduction. The Foreword outlines the central theme: the role that contemporary music plays in ministry to children and its impact on the spiritual development of young people.

Rajkumar begins by exploring the biblical foundations of music in worship, grounding his arguments in scriptural principles. He then discusses the cultural shifts that have influenced music over the years, particularly the rise of contemporary genres such as pop, rock, and hip-hop. Rajkumar's analysis of these genres is both insightful and respectful, recognizing their potential to convey deep spiritual truths when used appropriately. The author has adopted an interdisciplinary methodology, focusing on the spiritual formation approach to Christian education.

The study begins with an inquiry into the influence and significance of music in Christian worship. Music has a transformative ability to shape human emotions and impact society. The author discusses the diverse styles of Christian worship in vogue: formal-liturgical, traditional hymn-based, contemporary music-driven, charismatic, blended, and emerging worship. After briefly presenting the historical background of Christian music, its biblical and theological roots are explored. Significantly, music is not to be seen merely as a means of entertainment; rather, it is a powerful force that can heal the individual and awaken his/her spiritual energy. The author then proceeds to juxtapose the traditional and contemporary perspectives on using music in Christian worship. Older generations among the faithful and conservative clergy may be resistant to the introduction of modern music, preferring the deeper theological content of older hymns. In contrast, the appeal of modern music can attract younger generations, bring fresh energy into pastoral ministry, and draw more children to church. Hence, the need is to strike a balance between traditional and modern music to address the

real needs of children in the present context. Sunday School teachers and other pastoral workers need to be trained in new teaching methods as well as modern songs and music.

The book further delves into the spiritual formation approach to faith formation (page 59) as put forward by Susanne Johnson. This participatory approach involves incorporating spiritual practices like prayer, meditation, and worship into children's educational activities. Authentic spiritual growth is realized in an atmosphere of freedom, respect, trust, and intimacy. Spiritual formation must help individuals discover their vocation, awaken the divine image within themselves, discern God's grace in their lives, and identify factors that hinder the working of God's grace. The study continues to explore the theological approach to faith formation in the context of the specific role of children in building the Church and society. The theological approach values the wisdom of older generations and encourages children to discover and affirm their spiritual gifts. The ultimate aim of this approach is to accompany children on their journey to become authentic and committed disciples of Christ. One of the effective tools to engage children is modern music, which can positively influence children's beliefs and value systems.

The author delves into the specialized realm of the theology of music, examining its significant role in the spiritual formation of Christians. Emphasizing the importance of the message and content over the genre, the author argues that music can serve as a powerful tool for transmitting the Christian faith to younger generations. Advocating for a balanced approach that embraces both traditional and contemporary music, the author underscores the need for patience and tolerance. It is crucial to consider the preferences and needs of children when selecting music styles. The ministry among children is highlighted as essential for their comprehensive development, with particular emphasis on their spiritual growth. In this regard, modern music is identified as a potent medium for imparting gospel values to children (Page 82). The author encourages pastors and Sunday school teachers to leverage opportunities such as Vacation Bible School, camps, and retreats to teach the Christian faith in engaging and accessible ways. It is imperative that children perceive themselves as integral members of the local Church community.

In the concluding section, the author focuses on the critical role of music in the holistic development of children. The argument is made that to effectively connect with today's younger generation, it is essential to move beyond traditional musical forms and embrace contemporary genres. These modern styles offer innovative and exciting possibilities that resonate deeply with children and are contextually relevant. The author emphasizes that

ministry to children should aim not only for personal spiritual conversion but also for social transformation. Music, therefore, becomes a tool for educating children on important social issues such as justice, equality, and solidarity. Summarizing the study, the author notes, “The chapters in this book collectively underscore the Church’s need to recognize and harness the power of music, adapt to evolving cultural landscapes, prioritize children’s spiritual formation, and engage with contemporary musical trends. This approach is vital for effectively communicating the Christian message, fostering personal growth, and cultivating a dynamic and inclusive worship community” (p. 30).

The author has made a sincere attempt to move beyond routine conventional Christian education and offer an alternative, more creative and livelier ministry among children where contemporary music plays a pivotal role.

The book is a well-researched scientific work with sufficient footnotes and bibliography useful to the readers. Cover design is apt to the content. This educational book is a perfect resource for Church leaders, educators, and parents who are willing to invest in creative and inclusive ministry to children with contemporary music as the primary tool.

Reviewed by

Prof. Dr John Crasta

Editorial Board

